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Effect of Different Soil Amendments and season on root quality, shelf life and profitability of carrot (*Daucus carota* L.)

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Abstract

The objective for the study was to determine the effect of different rates of soil amendment and season on root quality, shelf life and profitability of carrot (*Daucus carota* L.) production in the transitional zone of Ghana. The experiment was laid out in a 10 x 2 factorial with treatments arranged in Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD). The factors were ten different rates of soil amendments and two seasons. The soil amendments used were: control (T_1), 5 ton/ha poultry manure (T_2), 45-45-45 kg/ha NPK, (T_3), 5 ton/ha compost (T_4), 7.5 ton/ha compost (T_5), 10 ton/ha compost (T_6), 50 % NPK + 2.5 ton/ha compost (T_7), 50 % NPK + 3.75 ton/ha compost (T_8), 50 % NPK + 5 ton/ha compost (T_9) and 50 % NPK + 2.5 ton/ha poultry manure (T_{10}). The seasons were major and minor. There were four replications. All data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using GENSTAT Version 11.1 (2008). The application of 7.5 ton/ha compost significantly showed greatest values for beta carotene, root cracking and total soluble solid. The control treatment had significantly the longest shelf life than the amended treatments. High ($P < 0.05$) cost of production was observed among carrot plants supplied with 10 ton/ha compost while the profit obtained was highest ($P < 0.05$) in the application of 7.5 ton/ha compost. With respect to season, weight loss of carrots at 15 DAH was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher in the major rainy season. The minor rainy season recorded the highest levels of vitamin C. The highest profit margin was observed in the major rainy season. This study concludes that 7.5 ton/ha compost promote bigger roots, root quality and maximize profit.

Keywords: Beta-carotene, vitamin C, root cracking, shrink carrots, profit margin

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Carrot is an important root vegetable crop belonging to the family Apiaceae, which produces edible leaves, taproot as well as seeds for propagation (Adeleye *et al.*, 2010; Atta Poku *et al.*, 2014). All over the world, people consume carrot in the raw state, cooked or in combination with other vegetables as ingredient of soup, dishes, sauces, juices and in dietary compositions (Warman and Havard, 1996). According to Rashidi and Khabbaz (2010) the plant is now extensively grown throughout the temperate zones. Carrots are now a popular vegetable grown all over the world including Ghana (Dawuda *et al.*, 2011; Benjamin and Hypolite, 2017). In Ghana, production is gradually expanding since the crop is among the most valuable exotic vegetables with high demand in urban centers and it is also exported for income. Root size and shape, colour, taste, quality and flavor are the most important selection parameters.

Carrot and other plants fulfill their nutritional requirements from uptake of minerals largely from the soil. Proper soil amendment and watering causes a significant difference in growth and yield of carrot (Dauda *et al.*, 2008; Atta Poku *et al.*, 2014). Carrots are fairly fussy growers and therefore require stone free, well drained,

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fertile soils with plenty of well decomposed organic matter (Bender *et al.*, 2009). Soils of the cultivated areas have an ability to promote plant growth with the nutrients held from previous crop rotation system or soil amendment programme. But these nutrients are not in sufficient amounts to meet the increasing requirements of carrots for higher productivity.

Soil nutrients applied on carrot plants are mainly utilized by the crops for growth and development. Left over nutrients in the soil leach down (Abdissa *et al.*, 2011) and become unavailable to the next crop. Resultantly, soils in the commercial crop growing areas do not hold sufficient quantity of nutrients to provide the amounts required by the plant for sustainable production and yield. In most cases, carrot growers use synthetic fertilizers as the major supply of nutrients in order to attain better growth and yield (Fritz, 2013; Dauda *et al.*, 2008).

Application of chemical fertilizers has, however, been associated with human health problems and environment degradation (Mufwanzala and Dikinya, 2010). Therefore, the nutrient management through organic sources of fertilizers to promote soil health and better plant nutrition has become increasingly important in recent years. Organic sources of fertilizers improve physico-chemical characteristics and fertility of soil in terms of organic matter, carbon, phosphorous, nitrogen contents, permeability, balanced supply of nutrients and plant available water capacity (Abdissa *et al.*, 2011).

Carrot yields in Ghana are very low as compared most neighboring countries which has been attributed to low soil fertility due to intensive cultivation on the same piece of land (Asiedu *et al.*, 2007), inadequate knowledge on the use of fertilizer from organic source and farmers inability to buy inorganic fertilizers due to high cost following the removal of government subsidy on inorganic fertilizers (Appiah *et al.*, 2017; Abdissa *et al.*, 2011).

Carrot yield and nutritional quality are affected by the types of fertilizers applied. Among the chemical constituents of the fertilizers, N plays a dominant role in affecting the nutritional quality (Starbuck, 2001). Carrot root yield was improved by one hundred percent recommended dose of N, P and K fertilizers compared to application of organic fertilizer alone or combined application of mineral and organic fertilizer (Hu and Barker, 2004). Nitrogen fertilization has received most attention of researchers with regard to root quality, its shelf life and profitability of carrot production in Ghana (Obeng, 2007).

The objective of the study was to determine the effect of different rates of soil amendment and season on root quality, shelf life and profitability of carrot (*Daucus carota L.*) production in the transitional zone of Ghana.

2.0 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Experimental Site

The study was conducted at Feyiase, which is located within the semi-deciduous forest zone of Ghana (7° 9' N, 2° 24' 0" W, 468) with two peaks of rainy seasons. It is characterized by double maxima rainfall. The first major rainfall season starts from March and ends in July. The second rainfall starts from September and ends in November. The mean annual rainfall is between 1600mm – 1800mm. It has a fairly high and uniform temperature ranging between 32°C in March and 20° C in August (Meteorological Service Department, 2017). Relative humidity is fairly moderate but high during the rainy season. It ranges between 70 and 80 percent in the dry season (FAOSTAT Database, 2012). The temperature regime and rainfall pattern enhance the cultivation of many food crops.

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Soil type at the site is Acrisol with good drainage (FAOSTAT Database, 2012). These soils have great agriculture value – they support all forms of arable crops with a considerable layer of organic matter. The site had been subjected to continuous cropping with maize and cassava as the main crops cultivated on the land. *Chromolaena odorata*, popularly called Acheampong shrubs seemed to be the predominant vegetative cover in many parts of the area (Meteorological Service Department, 2017).

2.2 Experimental Design and Treatment

The experiment was a 10 x 2 factorial with treatments arranged in Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD). The factors were two seasons and ten different rates of soil amendments. Each sub-plot measured 1.5 m x 2 m and the total area of the plot for the study was 250.0 m². The soil amendments used were: control (T₁), 5 ton/ha poultry manure (T₂), 45-45-45 kg/ha NPK, (T₃), 5 ton/ha compost (T₄), 7.5 ton/ha compost (T₅), 10 ton/ha compost (T₆), 50 % NPK + 2.5 ton/ha compost (T₇), 50 % NPK + 3.75 ton/ha compost (T₈), 50 % NPK + 5 ton/ha compost (T₉) and 50 % NPK + 2.5 ton/ha poultry manure (T₁₀). The seasons were major and minor. There were four replications.

2.3 Land Preparation and Cultural Practices

2.3.1 Land preparation

The site was cleared of all vegetation using manual labour. The debris was gathered into heaps outside the demarcated areas for controlled burning and to allow for ease of ploughing, harrowing, lining and pegging. Plots measuring 2 m x 1.5 m (3 m²) were demarcated and prepared manually using hoes and rakes. Each block was separated from the next by a distance of one metre. Where applicable, the manure and compost were incorporated into the soil and allowed to decompose for three weeks before beds were raised on each plot to about 30 cm high.

2.3.2 Sowing and cultural practices

Carrot seeds were sown by drilling. The beds were covered with palm fronds to minimize excessive heat and to prevent falling off of the seeds during watering. The palm fronds were removed seven days after planting when the seedlings have emerged from the soil. Watering was done every day using watering can except on rainy days. Thinning out was done 14 days after germination. Fertilizer (NPK-45, 45, 45) was applied on the respective plots after thinning out at the rate of 300 kg/ha.

Weeds were hand-picked as and when necessary. The paths between the blocks and plots were weeded using cutlass and hoe when the need arose. Earthening- up was carried out every two weeks to cover the root shoulders that have been exposed as a result of watering. Likewise the intra-rows were also stirred to improve aeration for proper growth and development of the crop.

2.4 Quality Parameters Measured

Samples were collected after harvesting from each treatment and were packaged in envelopes and stored in laboratory. Reducing sugar, total soluble sugars (TSS), root cracking, vitamin C and beta carotene were analyzed following procedures Okalebo *et al.* (2002).

2.5 Shelf Life

2.5.1 Weight loss after harvest

The taproots from each treatment were weighed using an electronic weighing scale after harvesting which was considered as the initial weight. Thereafter, weight of harvested carrots was taken every three days. Determination of shelf life of carrot lasted for 15 days after harvesting. Weight loss was calculated as the difference between the initial weights and the observed weight loss at every three days.

2.5.2 Percentage shrunked after harvest

The number of shrunked carrots from each treatment were counted and expressed in percentage.

2.5.3 Rooting percentage

Rooting percentage was observed after 15 days after harvesting. The rooting percentage was calculated by using the formular below.

$$\text{Rooting percentage} = \frac{\text{Number of rooten carrots}}{\text{Total number of harvested carrots}} \times 100$$

2.6 Cost Benefits Analysis

Average cost of seed, compost, poultry manure and N.P.K fertilizer was calculated per each treatment. Labour cost was computed by dividing the total expenditure on labour by the man-days of labour usage per farm during the production period. Average cost of other miscellaneous items was also calculated. The cost of production is the sum of the fixed cost and the variable cost of operation. That is, $C = FC + VC$ where C represents the total cost involved in carrot production, FC is the fixed cost and VC represents variable cost.

2.7 Statistical Analysis

The data collected were analyzed using the analysis of variance (ANOVA) using GenStat version 11.1 (2008), according to the procedure of Steel and Torrie (1980). The treatment means were separated by the Least Significant Difference (LSD) at 5 % probability level.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Initial Soil Chemical Properties at the Experimental Site

The results of the initial physico-chemical properties of soil at the experimental site are presented in Table 1. Results showed that the level of Al^{3+} ranges from 0.33 - 0.50 with mean value of 0.41, which falls within the normal range for sandy loamy soils (Landon, 1991). The available Ca^{2+} , H^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} and Na^+ contents were generally low according to the rating of Hazelton and Murphy (2007). This shows that application of external source of Ca^{2+} , H^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} and Na^+ is important for higher productivity of carrots. The soil was neutral with low mean organic matter content of 1.01 %. The available P content was medium ranging from 9.58 - 12.17 mg/kg with mean value of 10.87 mg/kg soil. This shows that the level of P in the soil is not adequate for carrot production (Landon, 1991).

The pH values ranged from 5.79 - 5.85 with mean of 5.82, which is slightly acidic according to the rating of Murphy (1968). The optimum pH for carrot production ranges between 5 and 8 (Nikus and Mulugeta, 2010). The organic carbon as well as that of total nitrogen content of the soil was medium according to the rating of Tekalign (1991). This shows that the soil was moderate in supplying organic carbon and nitrogen for plant growth and development (Snr *et al.*, 2020). Hence, it requires application of fertilizer for carrot production. The

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percentage clay and silt was moderate, while that of sand was high which was very good for carrot production. The bulk density of the soil ranged from 1.16 – 1.33 with mean value of 1.25. This bulk density falls within the normal range for sandy loams and un-compacted mineral soils (Landon, 1991). In general, the soil at Feyiase-Ashanti had low fertility status, which requires soil amendment Table 1.

3.2 Soil Nutrient Levels after Fertilizer Application

The result of the post harvested physico-chemical properties of soil at Feyiase-Ashanti in 2017 are presented in Table 2 (A and B). Different rates of soil amendment significantly ($P < 0.05$) increased the levels of Al, soil pH, percentage clay and soil bulk density. Although, no significant ($P > 0.05$) effect was observed on all the other soil properties, the mean values recorded were higher as compared to the initial physico-chemical properties of the soil. Results from the study shows that experimental plots amended with 5 ton/ha poultry manure recorded the highest ($P < 0.05$) level of Al, soil pH and soil bulk density with means of 0.48 cmol/kg soil, 6.22 and 1.29 Mg/m³. On the other hand, the control plots with no amendment recorded the least levels of Al, soil pH and soil bulk density with means of 0.10 cmol/kg soil, 5.75 and 1.15 Mg/m³. The control treatment recorded the highest ($P < 0.05$) percentage clay (7.00 %) with experimental plots amended with 0.113 ton/ha NPK + 5 ton/ha compost been the least. In general, the soil at Feyiase-Ashanti had improved in fertility status due to the various soil amendment applied to the soil.

3.3 Root quality

The effects of soil amendments on the root quality of carrots are presented in Table 3. Different rates of soil amendments had significant ($P < 0.05$) effect on beta-carotene, root cracking and total soluble solid. However, no significant ($P > 0.05$) effect was observed on reducing sugar and vitamin C. The level of beta carotene, root cracking and total soluble solid was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher among carrots plants amended with 7.5 ton/ha Compost. The control treatment recorded the least beta-carotene, root cracking and total soluble solid.

There was significant ($P < 0.05$) effect of season on the levels of vitamin C (Table 3) with the minor season recording greater than the major season. However, no significant ($P > 0.05$) seasonal effect was observed on beta-carotene, root cracking and total soluble solid (Table 3).

3.4 Shelf life of harvested roots

Different rates of soil amendments had significant ($P < 0.05$) effect on percentage weight loss, shrink carrots and rotting percentage at 15 days after harvesting (DAH) (Figure 1). Percentage weight loss at 15 DAH was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher among carrots plants amended with 50 % NPK + 5 ton/ha compost, and carrot plants amended with 50 % NPK + 2.5 ton/ha poultry manure recorded the least weight loss at 15 DAH. The percentage of shrink carrots at 15 DAH was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher among carrots plants amended with 50 % NPK + 5 ton/ha compost, and carrot plants of the control treatment recorded the least shrink. Similarly, rotting percentage at 15 DAH was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher among carrots plants amended with 50 % NPK + 5 ton/ha compost, while the control treatment recorded the least rotting percentage at 15 DAH (Figure 1).

There was significant ($P < 0.05$) effect of season on the percentage weight loss at 15 DAH (Figure 2). However, no significant ($P > 0.05$) effect was observed on shrink carrots and rotting percentage at 15 DAH. Weight loss of carrots at 15 DAH was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher in the major rainy season and lower (12.81) in the minor rainy season (Figure 2). There was no significant ($P > 0.05$) interaction effect.

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3.5 Production cost, income and profit in carrot production

Different rates of soil amendments had significant ($P < 0.05$) effect on the production cost, income and profit. The highest cost of production was significantly observed among carrot plants amended with 10 ton/ha compost, and the lowest in the control treatment. Income generated from the sales across the various treatments was highest among carrot plants amended with 45-45-45 kg/ha NPK treatment and lowest in the control treatment. Considering the cost involved and the income obtained, the profit margin was highest in the 7.5 ton/ha compost treatment and lowest in the control treatment. The effect of season on the production cost, income and profit was not significant ($P > 0.05$). Similarly, there was no significant ($P > 0.05$) interaction effect.

Table 4.1: Initial physico-chemical properties of soil at experimental site

Soil property	Min	Max	Mean	SD
Chemical properties				
Soil pH (1:1 H ₂ O)	5.79	5.85	5.82	0.04
Organic matter (%)	1.00	1.03	1.01	1.02
Total N (%)	0.05	0.06	0.05	0.004
Available P (mg/kg soil)	9.58	12.17	10.87	1.82
Exchangeable cations (cmol/kg soil)				
Ca ²⁺ (cmol/kg soil)	2.16	2.82	2.49	0.46
Mg ²⁺	0.34	0.44	0.39	0.07
K ⁺	0.30	0.33	0.31	0.02
Na ⁺	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.00
Al ³⁺	0.33	0.50	0.41	0.11
H ⁺	0.17	0.17	0.16	0.00
Physical properties				
Sand (%)	79.40	81.32	80.36	1.35
Silt (%)	10.36	13.36	11.86	2.12
Clay (%)	7.24	8.32	7.78	0.76
Texture	Sandy loam			
Bulk density (Mg/m ³)	1.16	1.33	1.25	0.12
Soil organic carbon (%)	0.58	0.60	0.59	0.01

Values are means of duplicate sample analyses. SD = Standard deviation, CV = Coefficient of variation.

Table 2: Soil chemical properties after fertilizer application

Soil amendment	Chemical properties (cmol/kg soil)						
	Al ³⁺	Ca ²⁺	K ⁺	Mg ²⁺	Na ⁺	N (%)	Soil pH
Control (No soil amendment)	0.10	2.29	0.26	1.38	0.27	0.07	5.76
5 ton/ha Poultry manure	0.48	2.02	0.23	1.17	0.29	0.07	6.22
45-45-45 kg/ha NPK	0.46	2.58	0.25	1.41	0.29	0.07	5.91
5 ton/ha Compost	0.26	2.55	0.27	1.17	0.32	0.06	5.97
7.5 ton/ha Compost	0.21	2.82	0.28	1.22	0.32	0.07	6.06
10 ton/ha Compost	0.13	2.82	0.27	1.38	0.30	0.07	6.13
50 % NPK + 2.5 ton/ha Compost	0.30	2.74	0.23	1.57	0.32	0.09	5.92
50 % NPK + 3.75 ton/ha Compost	0.15	2.42	0.36	1.30	0.32	0.07	6.19
50 % NPK + 5 ton/ha Compost	0.32	2.45	0.57	1.06	0.43	0.06	6.05
50 % NPK + 2.5 ton/ha PM	0.30	2.43	0.30	1.14	0.33	0.06	5.93
LSD (0.05)	0.17	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	0.23
CV (%)	40.50	17.53	62.1	38.3	18.8	22.01	2.80

Table 2B: Soil physical and chemical properties after fertilizer application

Soil amendment	Organic matter (%)	SOC (%)	Clay (%)	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Bulk density (Mg/m ³)
Control (No soil amendment)	1.23	0.71	7.00	61.31	34.50	1.15
5 ton/ha Poultry manure	1.26	0.73	5.00	83.50	11.50	1.29
45-45-45 kg/ha NPK	1.20	0.69	5.00	82.02	13.03	1.27
5 ton/ha Compost	1.23	0.71	4.50	84.51	11.01	1.19
7.5 ton/ha Compost	1.30	0.75	5.50	81.52	13.01	1.25
10 ton/ha Compost	1.33	0.77	6.00	84.52	9.52	1.26

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50 % NPK + 2.5 ton/ha Compost	1.61	0.93	6.00	82.51	11.51	1.23
50 % NPK + 3.75 ton/ha Compost	1.29	0.75	4.50	83.51	12.03	1.25
50 % NPK + 5 ton/ha Compost	1.15	0.67	4.00	84.00	12.00	1.26
50 % NPK + 2.5 ton/ha PM	1.12	0.65	4.00	85.51	10.51	1.27
LSD (0.05)	NS	NS	1.20	NS	NS	0.42
CV (%)	18.50	18.50	16.20	12.30	81.70	15.42

Table 3: Root quality due to treatment effects

Treatment	Beta carotene (mg g ⁻¹)	Reducing sugar (mg g ⁻¹)	Root cracking (%)	Total Soluble Solid (%)	Vitamin C mg g ⁻¹
Soil amendment					
Control (No soil amendment)	0.05	3.93	2.22	49.55	0.08
5 ton/ha Poultry manure	0.06	3.85	2.43	57.01	0.10
45-45-45 kg/ha NPK	0.06	3.40	2.56	52.23	0.12
5 ton/ha Compost	0.06	3.82	2.53	53.58	0.09
7.5 ton/ha Compost	0.07	3.51	2.91	59.50	0.08
10 ton/ha Compost	0.06	3.95	2.24	50.83	0.09
50 % NPK + 2.5 ton/ha Compost	0.05	3.38	2.42	53.48	0.14
50 % NPK + 3.75 ton/ha Compost	0.06	3.11	2.80	55.21	0.10
50 % NPK + 5 ton/ha Compost	0.06	3.58	2.36	55.48	0.14
50 % NPK + 2.5 ton/ha PM	0.06	3.33	2.29	55.91	0.11
LSD (0.05)	0.01	NS	0.37	3.97	NS
CV (%)	8.20	18.81	15.32	7.30	47.70
Season					
Major rainy season	0.06	3.71	2.50	53.99	0.09
Minor rainy season	0.06	3.47	2.46	54.56	0.12
LSD (0.05)	NS	NS	NS	NS	0.02
CV (%)	11.10	19.11	17.01	8.70	46.40

Figure 1: Effect of different rates of soil amendment on shelf life of roots

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Figure 2: Effect of season on the shelf life of roots

Table 4: Production cost, income and profit margin

Treatment	Cost of production (Gh¢/ha)	Income (Gh¢/ha)	Profit (Gh¢/ha)
Soil amendment			
Control (No soil amendment)	38.50	71.25	32.75
5 ton/ha Poultry manure	40.17	91.88	51.70
45-45-45 kg/ha NPK	40.58	110.62	66.85
5 ton/ha Compost	40.35	77.50	37.15
7.5 ton/ha Compost	41.27	83.12	70.05
10 ton/ha Compost	42.20	91.25	49.05
50 % NPK + 2.5 ton/ha Compost	40.46	90.62	50.16
50 % NPK + 3.75 ton/ha Compost	40.92	86.88	45.95
50 % NPK + 5 ton/ha Compost	41.39	91.25	49.86
50 % NPK + 2.5 ton/ha PM	40.37	96.88	56.51
LSD (0.05)	0.18	7.90	7.54
CV (%)	8.50	2.20	15.00

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Root quality

Carrots plants supplied with 7.5 ton/ha compost was of high quality as compared to the control and the other treatment groups. The significant improvement in beta carotene, total soluble solid and reduction in root cracking observed among carrot plants amended in 7.5 ton/ha compost might be due to the availability of essential plant nutrients and high N, P and K use efficiency during the growing period of the plant. According to Evanylo *et al.* (2008), application of compost in carrot production improved total soluble solid and reduced the sugar content of roots produced as compared to by plants that received poultry manure as well as the control treatment. The authors further observed that the application of compost in carrot production improved vitamin level and other essential amino acids. Furthermore, as the rate of compost increased the total soluble solid and sugar content decreased. Starbuck (2001) reported that humic substance is the major component of soil organic matter in composts which increased root size and quality via hormonal effects on root elongation and plant development.

4.2 Shelf life of harvested roots

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The major factors that limit the shelf life of harvested roots of carrots are; high respiration rate, development of off-flavours, acidification, loss of firmness, discoloration and microbial spoilage (Barry-Ryan and O'Beirne, 2000). In this study, the highest weight loss, shrunk carrots and rotting percentage was observed among carrot plants amended with 50 % NPK + 2.5 ton/ha compost, 50 % NPK + 5 ton/ha compost and 50 % NPK + 5 ton/ha compost respectively due to high levels of water in the roots as a result of the application of NPK fertilizer. Sharma *et al.* (2003) reported that the application of 50 % NPK + 2.5 ton/ha poultry manure was superior to the fertilizer combinations in terms of the quality of carrot produced. This result collaborates with the findings of Pimentel *et al.* (2009) who conducted a field experiment to evaluate the agronomic yield and quality of carrot after application of organic manure and reported that the quality of carrot produced was improved as a result of the application of compost.

In this study carrot plants harvested in the major rainy season recorded the highest weight loss and this could be attributed to excessive rainfall and excessive accumulation of water in the harvested roots. Similar result was also reported by Bender *et al.* (2009), who stated that carrot roots absorbed more water during the major rainy season as compared to carrot plant harvested during the minor rainy season. Pimentel *et al.* (2009) conducted a field experiment in Brazil to evaluate the agronomic yield and quality of carrot after application of organic manure and reported that weight loss of harvested carrot is high during the major rainy season where there is high accumulation of water due to excessive rain fall.

4.3 Production cost, income and profit in carrot production

The least cost of production was observed in the control treatment as compared to the soil amendment treatment due to the fact that little amount of money was spent on soil management with no amendment. The significant high cost of production incurred in the application of the different rates of soil amendments as compared to the control treatment might be due to the large quantities of the various levels of organic and inorganic fertilizer used and the cost of application.

The significant differences in the profit margin observed in the application of 7.5 ton/ha compost could be explained that higher marketable roots were obtained as compared to the other amendment groups. Similar findings were reported by Pimentel *et al.* (2009) and Anon (2007). On the contrary, Dawuda *et al.* (2011) investigated on the influence of soil amendment rates and spacing on production cost, income and profit and the authors reported that the application of 15 ton/ha and 20 ton/ha poultry manure gave more profit than the application of compost. The variations in the two findings can be attributed to the differences in the levels of poultry manure used in the various experiment.

4. CONCLUSION

This study concludes that, the application of 7.5 ton/ha compost and major rain season promotes root quality such as beta carotene content, root cracking and total soluble solids. The control treatment had the longest shelf life than the soil amendment treatments. High cost of production was observed among carrot plants supplied with 10 ton/ha compost. This study also concludes that, the highest profit margin was obtained from the application of 7.5 ton/ha compost.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors of this manuscript have declared that no competing interests exist.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. Author JSA, VL and PAP Snr. designed the study, wrote the protocol and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Author CGK and PAP Snr. performed the statistical analysis, managed the analyses of the study and managed the literature searches. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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